

Types of caries and treatment methods

Shamsiddinov Mironshox

Bukhara University of innovative education and medicine

Abstract: This pathology can be called, without exaggeration, "the dental enemy of humanity number 1." 93% of the world's population suffers from this disease. It was found even in people who lived 5-6 thousand years ago, and today caries in adults is the cause of tooth loss in almost 90% of cases. Moreover, it leads not only to the formation of well-known "holes". Later, when the pathological process begins to spread to the surrounding areas, this causes the appearance of periodontitis, and then complete destruction of the tooth, which requires the irrevocable removal of its remains and root.

Key words: caries, teeth, dental, plaque.

Dental caries is the demineralization and decay of the tooth hard tissue, in which a cavity is formed in the tooth. The enamel floor of the tooth is accompanied by a pigmented yellowish-brown spot, unpleasant odor from the mouth, pain when eating sweet, salty, spicy, cold or hot products. As a result of the deepening of caries, the development of a cyst, pulpitis, then periodontitis is possible. Failure to treat caries in time causes tooth loss. In addition, caries causes acute or chronic diseases to hurt.

Dental caries is a violation, decay of the integrity of the hard enamel layer of the tooth, the bone floor under the influence of a ditrophic or infectious factor.

Causes of caries

The disease is considered one of the very common pathologies among the population. According to WHO statistics, caries occurs in 80% to 98% of people in different countries and among different races. For the last two years, the disease has become widespread among children, especially in the population living in economically underdeveloped countries, caries diseases in it has been observed to occur to varying degrees. Dental caries is not considered an independent disease, this pathology is caused by general changes in the body. For example, a decrease in local and general immunity, changes in the gastrointestinal system play an important role in the formation of caries. Currently, there are more than 400 theories that explain the cause of the origin of caries. However, in many of the theories, a coating is formed on the tooth enamel in the case when the oral hygiene is not followed, and this coating leads to caries. The coating develops as a result of constant tooth cleaning or improper cleaning, especially in areas where the tooth edge of the teeth is poorly touched (dental flanks, wisdom teeth). The dental coating gets a strong

coating on the enamel floor of the tooth and is considered to have favorable conditions for these bacteria (streptococcal flora). The mineral substances contained in the saliva cause the coating to harden. Such a coating that forms on the tooth is called dental plaque.

Diagnosis and treatment of caries

Caries is detected by stomatologists at the time of visual examination or with the help of instrumental examinations. Complaints in the patient help to diagnose caries. The main treatment for caries is to remove the affected area of the tooth and replace it with a filling. The affected area is completely removed, and its place is disinfected. The better the disinfection procedure is carried out, the better the sealant will be of good quality and will last a long time. Currently, the laser method is used to remove damaged areas of dental caries. The effective aspects of the method are the absence of pain, noisiness and the quality of the tooth for filling. Treatment of surface caries is carried out in several ways. Of these, the most common method is “scraping” (shlifying) and reminerylation of carious areas of the tooth. The practice of reminerylation is achieved by administration of 1% sodium fluoride using appliqué or electrophoresis. The mid-level caries is treated with the removal of the affected tooth area and its position with plombation.

References:

1. Bakhritdinov, F. S., Matkarimov, Z. T., Azimova, M. T., Saatova, U. M., Komilova, D. N., & Elmurodova, N. B. (2022). Features of Pregnancy Management in Kidney Transplant Recipients. *Experimental and Clinical Transplantation: Official Journal of the Middle East Society for Organ Transplantation*, 20(Suppl 4), 92-97.
2. Dental caries: clinical recommendations (treatment protocols) /Dental Association of Russia. 2014.